

ISic3355

Funerary altar for Thalpon

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.07 and checked 30.09.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

contrada Reina, close to the railway line to Noto, found 13.05.1930

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 49370

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 57 cm

Width 31 cm

Depth 20 cm

Layout

Text is set out over six lines within a panel of 26 x 21 cm in the form of a tabula ansata

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Lunate omega, sigma and epsilon; alpha, lamda and delta have extended upper strokes; mu appears in two forms on line 2, typical later form with tall upper strokes and at line end a small rounded form mid-line; xi on line 4 is formed of two horizontals with a detached curved stroke between. The repetition of the deceased's name on line 3 is marked off by a large comma-shaped interpunct.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-6: 15-25 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Θάλπων χάρει
2. χρηστὲ καὶ ἄμεμ
3. πτε · Θάλπων
4. ἐνθάδε κεῖμαι ἕξα
5. ετῆς δὲ θανῶν
6. νήπιος ὠκύμορος

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Thalpon, farewell, worthy and blameless Thalpon! Here I lie, having died aged six, a child of swift fate.

Translation (it)

Talpone, addio, buono ed irreprensibile Talpone! Qui giaccio, e morto a sei anni, bambine di celere fato.

Commentary

The name Thalpon is not otherwise attested.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644860

Bibliography

Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At 217-218 no.99

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3355. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358422>

Photo J.Prag: Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del
06/05/2014